

If Only: Bringing Dreams into Practice

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Abstract

This paper introduces the IF ONLY method for investigating users emotions through games. References are made to game and theatre theory and the method is explained with examples from the FARAWAY project. The game: “this is how i feel” is described and the paper concludes with some examples of game results and conclusions.

Keywords: Emotions, interaction design, games, game theory, participatory design, user engagement, expression.

Introduction

As the remit of design is broadened, interaction design is beginning to deliberately and actively investigate and use concepts like emotions, experience and affection and as a result new sets of challenges are emerging. Recognising that using a product is an ‘experience’ that goes beyond the accomplishment of a task, creates a new need to define approaches and techniques that will allow us to understand and anticipate the nature of this experience while we design. Traditional user research methods typically focus on tasks and activities. People are observed and interviewed in order to understand how they perform a specific task in a lab setting or within the natural context of their normal life. This sometimes involves using experimental prototypes in order to evaluate how the designers can support them in reaching a given goal or solving a problem.

However, in the last couple of years, a shift of focus has begun. Nathan Shedroff (Shedroff, 2003) points out that we can look at all design as ‘experience design’, meaning that regardless of the medium the focus of our design processes should be the creation of a particular user experience. According to Shedroff this also implies devising new tools for designers to understand “*what makes a good experience first, and then to translate these principles, as well as possible, into the desired media without the technology dictating the*

form of the experience". An interesting answer to this need is the concept of 'experience prototyping' developed by IDEO. According to Buchenau and Fulton Suri (2000) an "experience prototype is any kind of representation, in any medium, that is designed to understand, explore or communicate what it might be like to engage with the product, space or system we are designing". Experience prototyping puts the emphasis on any kind of contextual, sensorial, physical and cognitive factors that define an active engagement into an interaction. As the authors argue this kind of process is not new in design practices; however it is this conscious emphasis on the complexity of the experience and the effort of *establishing an attitude* that makes it relevant and original. By designing and experimenting with different experience prototyping techniques and by reflecting on their motivations and implications, these methods are contributing to a reflection on new design practices that can potentially overcome the limitations of traditional methods.

Through this paper we aim at contributing to this discussion by introducing our approach, the IF ONLY games. We are interested in exploring design ideas by focusing specifically on the emotional aspect of the experience. How can we access people's emotions in a design process? How do we access and collect these private and subjective aspects of human experience? In the following we will introduce the general framework of our approach and discuss through practical examples how our ideas can be embodied into a replicable set of techniques.

A game of possibilities: If only

Emotions are by definition difficult to isolate, observe or measure. The IF ONLY games try to overcome this limitation by creating *artificial* contexts where people can engage themselves through *real* emotional involvement. Our approach has its origin in the notion that the emotional value of a design object can be explored through experiments and by creating prototype experiences for users. The IF ONLY games are designed to investigate the emotional impact of our design ideas in an iterative process before, while and after the design process.

The key concept of the IF ONLY is game play. We use game play in an attempt to engage and immerse the whole person, emotionally and logically, into our design process. This is done by creating a conceptual framework in the form of a game that will sustain the player's suspension of disbelief as they immerse themselves in the possibilities of the design space.

These frameworks support the player to express otherwise inaccessible emotional needs, to envision a possible future or alternative reality and to enable collaborative and situated concept development. The full immersion of players into the design space together with a game's ability to grant temporary empowerment and freedom from responsibility increases the possibilities for engagement between the designers and the people we are designing for.

Game lessons

Ludwig Wittgenstein (1953) pointed out that there is no common nature of games. Some but not all games are amusing or involve competition but there is only a network of 'overlapping and criss-crossing' similarities between games, not a common feature running through all games. However, several theoretical disciplines have developed relevant theories that begin to approach the nature of gaming and play.

One of the most interesting aspects of games and game play is the concept of '**make-believe**'. Caillois (1958) underlines how playing means moving to another reality, where the rules of the real world are replaced with precise and essential rules that the person playing must adapt to. This implies that, in order to play, one must believe in this alternative world as if it was the 'real' one. This acceptance of the game's rules must be voluntary and free, as freedom and choice are characteristics of playing itself. The narrative framework of a game enables players to accept rules and constraints that deviate from their everyday life whilst maintaining a feeling of freedom and spontaneity. This is supported by the fact that the game occurs within a time and space constraint that is identified and set beforehand. It is temporary and we enter into it knowing that it will end and we will be able to repossess our everyday life and role when the game is over. In this way the experience of the game is safely confined within the game space and does not necessarily have consequences in the outside world. 'Make-believe' is somehow missing from traditional user research methods. We can ask people what they do, feel and experience in an existing situation or what they would do, feel and experience in a possible new situation whilst having at their disposal something we want to design. Alternatively we can use simulations by explicitly asking users to interact with new artefacts, services, systems 'as if' they were already part of their normal life. In both cases the user's identification into these realities will happen mostly at a rational level. Thanks to its special mechanisms the game format can support this process better: because they have

accepted the rules of the game voluntarily the players (or users) are likely to accept the whole context of the test experience and fully engage with it.

Two other key concepts are ‘**immersion**’ and ‘**involvement**’. Although most games have no consequences in 'real life' they still have the power to prompt someone's real cognitive and emotional participation. Csikszentmihalyi (1990) uses playing as an example of the highly energized and enjoyable state of concentration and focus that he defines as ‘flow’. This means that by entering play-mode a person is able to fully engage in a task or activity, while at the same time have a pleasurable and fun experience. In terms of design prototyping this implies that the play-mode can be used to trigger more emotional participation from users than traditional methods.

Playing games can also be a way of supporting **expression** and **creativity**. While some games build on cognitive skills (e.g. strategic games, educational games) others specifically prompt less rationale modes of participation. As surrealist and situationist artists discovered, games can provide an alternative reality that allows people to let down their guard, access the unconscious, express how they feel and think and cross boundaries they might not have otherwise crossed. Through playful procedures and methodologies of the fantastic, surrealist games lead to ‘out of the ordinary’ situations where the player is allowed to express her or himself in a spontaneous and genuinely way. For example, in one of the more direct surrealist techniques, automatic writing (Gooding 1995), participants are encouraged to write whatever comes to mind in a *stream of consciousness* style where nothing is corrected or rewritten. The unexpected material produced by this free associative writing game reveals unconscious thoughts and desires that may not otherwise be accessed or addressed. Applying games to design prototyping can in a similar way elicit emotional and otherwise inaccessible content and to trigger creative future-oriented thinking.

The IFONLY games start from these premises. Games offer an opportunity for user-centred design and research to understanding the existing and anticipating the new. Games and prototyping have already been incorporated in some design practices. However, our objective is to initiate reflections on how these insights can be transformed into a structured set of tools for designers. By adopting game mechanisms we have an opportunity to not only collect desires, emotions and expressions that people would otherwise rarely express in the context

of user research, but also experiment and simulate design possibilities while capturing emotional responses and impact of prototypes.

The anatomy of a game: Faraway

In the following we will take an example from FARAWAY – a project aiming to create interactions using sensory and symbolic aspects of emotions between people who are physically distant but emotionally close. People in intimate relationships usually develop a universe of specific codes, languages and references that identify their private mode of communication. These elements become the constituents of an alternative emotional space that people enter while communicating with their loved ones. The field of emotional communication is very private and therefore difficult to access through current methods like observation, interviews and traditional prototyping techniques. The IF ONLY games were used in this project to overcome this barrier in a playful setting by reproducing this emotional space as a framework for the players to experience alternative modes of communication. Each game invites the players to experiment with a new and unusual way of communicating presence and emotions within the emotional space created by an affective relationship: by creating objects, by wearing particular clothes, by sharing physiological information, etc. To explain how IF ONLY games were created in the context of FARAWAY we will refer to the first game we played with users. The game is called: “this is how I feel”.

Figure 1, The first game invitation card which initiates the games and introduces DistantOne.

The card reads:

an invitation to the game of
~ THIS IS HOW I FEEL ~

You find yourself in a small town. You did not use to live here.
You arrived from somewhere else. Let's call it
BiggerCity. You left someone behind. Let's call that person
DistantOne.

THERE IS A BOX ON YOUR TABLE
Unwrap the box. Open the box.
Taste a Leone. Empty the rest onto the table.

Take the weekend. Ask yourself how you are feeling. You want to
send this feeling to DistantOne. What does this feeling look like?
Can you taste it? Can you smell it?

Take this feeling and put it in the box. What would you call this
feeling? Put the name of the feeling on the outside of the box.
Leave the box on your desk on Monday morning.

~ IF ONLY ~

This game initiates the project, inviting the player to participate. The games were conducted at the Interaction Design Institute Ivrea with students and staff and the theme of displacement was directly mirroring many of the players experience as most of them had relocated recently. DistantOne is introduced as the loved person with whom the player wants to communicate. The player is asked to express an experienced emotion within the three-dimensional space of a candy box. By collecting and analysing these communications instead of actually allowing them to be exchanged, the results are a series of one-way messages from the players. The overall objective is to introduce and establish an emotional connection between the individual players and IF ONLY, and to test the player's willingness to play as well as generate an index of representations of emotions. The specific focus is of "this is how I feel" is on the modalities of expression of emotional content and the related levels of earnestness and intimacy. Through this game we aimed at understanding if the idea of using physical objects to transmit emotions over distance was meaningful for our players and what would be the modes of expressions they would use; furthermore, we looked for emotional tokens that would trigger the creativity of the players. In the following we will discuss some of the design aspects of the game.

Separation

We believe that the time and space constraints Caillois identifies are important in order to provoke immersion and make believe. For this reason, the games we design have temporal and spatial boundaries. However, depending on the context in which they are played, the constraints are flexible enough to adapt to people's needs and times of response. In the case of "this is how I feel" we aimed at separating the activity of game playing from the daily work activities of our users by asking them to respond during the weekend and bring back the results the following Monday.

Surprise

The element of surprise is crucial to the IF ONLY games and can be seen as a mechanism for catching potential players off guard and encouraging participation. In this case the cards were left on the players desks to be discovering in the morning. There were no prior agreement with the players and no warning that the games were about to begin. Along with the card a box of candy was also left on the desk and together the invitation was designed to appear as a

nice surprise, like a gift. Another possible way to obtain the surprise effect could be sending invitations by mail or email.

Language and Style

Language is used to create an emotional atmosphere encouraging people to join a playful game as opposed to being subjects of an experiment. In the same way, a subjective visual and verbal language is created to prompt people's participation to the games. The card starts by telling the players that they are invited to the game of "this is how i feel". Underneath there is an illustration of the candy box followed by the text. The text is divided into two parts; the first part is written as a narrative, setting the game in context, concluded with a key sentence in all caps, followed by the actual task or rule for the game. The language is second person addressing the players as 'you' and utilizing coaxing suggestive vocabulary. The coaxing tone invites the players to participate in a supportive manner without being prescriptive. The tone is deliberately remnant of the voice of an old fashioned hypnotiser, setting the scene of the session first by describing it and then allowing the 'hypnosis subject' to assume the role of protagonist and 'continue the story'. On this card we tell the players that they are finding themselves in 'SmallTown', and we introduce the role of 'DistantOne'. SmallTown is a suggestive expression of the feeling of displacement and distance that we wanted to establish as the basis for the communication with 'DistantOne', the symbolic name for the loved one the player is communicating with.

Props

In some situations props can act as containers of symbolic content and be used to strengthen the relationship between people (Storm, 2001). Howard (2002) regards props as necessary to maintain a link to reality and in that sense props can be seen as tools for interacting with context. In the FARAWAY game, the box is a prop but one that changes status as the game progresses from a neutral and nice surprise to a carrier for a private emotional message. The invitation card itself is also a prop and great care was taken with its design and production.

Expression

IF ONLY games are not competitive (*agôn*, in Caillois' terms) nor chance-based (what Caillois calls *alea*). Instead, they simply invite people to perform a task in a playful way. The task of the game is to express a feeling as a gift for someone you love. While the rules are specific 'take this feeling and put it in the box' the design space in which the task can be

performed is vast. The task takes a complex concept, an emotion, which is by definition impossible to express fully and suggests that it be expressed though an 'impossible' medium, the limited three dimensional space inside a given box. The underlying idea is to counter an impossibility with another impossibility. Within the scope of the games this logical contradiction is meant to liberate the player from the difficulty of the undertaking and encourage lateral thinking. There is no element of competition as this is a highly private matter between each player and DistantOne. None of the games are using elements of competition and there is no concept of failing or winning.

The message in the box

The game generated a large variety of responses. 27 boxes were returned and consequently spirited away from the desks of the players.

Figure 2, An emotion in a box.
The box is labelled: *'I can still hear you'* and contains a sea shell.

'I can hear you' is an example of response where the player used an object to create an emotional experience for the loved person. The seashell contained in the candy box is an invitation for the receiver to listen to a sound that is emotionally charged for the sender.

The players put written texts, colours, textures, images, objects, combinations of objects, etc. in their boxes. Many of them tried to communicate physical sensations like warmth and coldness, light or shining by using objects with particular sensorial properties (e.g. metal for cold); others created a suggestive experience for their DistantOnes by providing them with tools to interact with. The width of the responses gave the FARAWAY project a inspiring index of possible modalities to explore in the games that followed. This first game also confirmed our initial assumptions about people' willingness to exchange emotional content, even with a semi-fictional character. A more specific conclusion concerning the nature of the game was that the task people found most difficult was generating a verbal description for the represented emotion.

I got a little frustrated trying to resolve the complexity of it in a single word. (C.)

I found choosing a word to describe what I felt was very standard, I mean, it was impossible. (A.)

Words are normally considered as a natural and effective way to communicate to someone else how or what we feel. This game suggests how other media can be powerful in translating our inner states into a message. It also gave us an initial appreciation of the potential strength of the symbolic value of physical objects when combined with sensorial properties and the box-messages were used to inform the following steps of FARAWAY. We went on to create other games that explored more specifically the qualities of the tokens that were collected during this first game, in particular: warmth and light (fig. 3).

Figure 3, ‘ping’ touch-light communicator. As the touch sensors on one bean is activated the corresponding light on the other bean lights up.

Some conclusions

The games created for the FARAWAY project were a success in terms of make-believe, engagement and level of real emotional involvement of the players. The results of the many games played throughout the research, design and prototyping phases of the project not only inspired and informed the design but set the direction and the focus for the project. By using the cards, objects and situations we provided the players with, as artefacts of the experience, we were able to infer both qualitative and quantitative results. Our tacit knowledge gained through observing the performance of the games together with visual documentation, such as game cards, photographs and objects created strong arguments for formulating new games and concepts as well as introducing new design ideas.

The design of the IF ONLY style and rules is ongoing and the method is being developed to be used in various other projects. The biggest challenge of the IF ONLY games is the capture of peoples’ experiences and expression. The game referred to in this paper is an example of a game dedicated entirely to the creative expression of an emotion and the capture of that creative expression.

The method for creating a generic IF ONLY game can be summed up like this:

- Defining the objective.
 - In the case of FARAWAY: emotional intensity, alternative modalities of communication and possibilities for symbolic non-lingual messages.
- Creation of situation and strategy.
 - Selection of players, timing and locations appropriate to the objective.
 - Creating the framework narrative to mirror the real life of the players and focus on the objective.
- Creation of props. This is done while keeping in mind the objective and strategy.
 - The candy box with its empty space inside provides room for capturing expression of intended emotion.
 - The card is specifically created to stir emotions, set the stage and put the game into play.
- Method of collection
 - Using the desks as a place to leave messages and collect results after hours.
 - Observation, registration and analysis of results.

Interaction is a relatively new field and one that deals almost exclusively with people's relationships with technology. As information technology gets more personal and invades more areas of our lives, these relationships and their sub themes of privacy, comfort, trust and expression will become the areas where design products succeed or fail. When we are designing these objects with their capabilities to create new kinds of relations between people and their surroundings, we have the possibility to involve not only the need of the user but also the desires, the dreams and the fears. IF ONLY is created to take the emotions and situations of the prospective user seriously into consideration before, during and after a design process. It is our hope that methods like these can result in products and protocols that work for and support the emotional life of our users and that we can find ways of bridging the gap between the playful IF ONLY reality and the everyday experience.

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Kristina Andersen works with interactions and concepts to create unusual objects, protocols and experiences using iterative processes informed by games and play. She holds an MA specialising in wearable computers, an M.Sc specialising in tangible objects in virtual spaces, and was a research fellow at the Interaction Design Institute Ivrea, where in collaboration with Margot Jacobs and Laura Polazzi she worked on the FARAWAY project. Other recent projects include whisper, in collaboration with Thecla Schiphorst and Suzan Kozel, where the emphasis lies on using physiological data as input for an audio-visual environment and responsive intelligent garments. She is currently artist in residence at STEIM (Studio for Electro-Instrumental Music) in Amsterdam working on 'ensemble', a set of sensor-based wearable musical controllers developed for musical experiences for children. She is mentor at DasArts (School for Advanced Research in Theatre and Dance) and honorary visiting design fellow at the University of York. www.lockergirl.com

Margot Jacobs is an interaction design researcher focusing on playful, emotional incorporation of technology in everyday life. She holds a deep interest in developing innovative design methods and experimental prototypes for social interventions in public space. Currently, Margot works as an interaction design researcher at the PLAY studio of the Interactive Institute. Her previous experience includes a year as research fellow at the interaction Design Institute Ivrea, Italy. Margot holds a bachelor's degree in Industrial Design from the Georgia Institute of Technology and a master's degree from the Interactive Telecommunications Program in New York. Margot takes a great interest in reaching the public and other audiences. Her work has been shown at international venues including SIGGRAPH, VIDA LIFE, ISWC, UBICOMP, NIFCA, ISEA etc. Outreach activities include organizing local creative new media collective [fringe], lecturing, tutoring postgraduate students, and co-founding BIG LOVE, a gallery space for community expression.

Laura Polazzi is a user experience designer. Her main focus is on understanding people's behaviors, needs and desires and designing concepts for innovative applications. Her professional competences include creating user profiles (personas), conducting prototype evaluation, developing concepts and information architecture for websites and investigating new trends in the design domain. She studied communication and Human-computer interaction at the University of Siena (Italy) and ergonomics (MA) at the University of Liège (Belgium). She has been a researcher at the University of Liège (Belgium), and at Interaction Design Institute Ivrea (Italy), where she developed Faraway with Kristina Andersen and Margot Jacobs. She keeps collaborating with Interaction Design Institute Ivrea, where she is responsible for user research in several innovation projects, including Fluidtime, ViVi (in collaboration with Telecom Italia) and Multipla+ (in collaboration with FIAT). As a consultant she has worked for companies such as Ideo, Grey Interactive Italia, GPF and Motorola.